

DEVELOPMENT OF CYCLIC DAMAGE IN CARBON EPOXY COMPOSITES UNDER VARIABLE LOADING CONDITIONS

A. Plumtree and J. H. Dahl

Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada

Corresponding author (plumtree@uwaterloo.ca)

Keywords: CFRP $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ and $[45]_8$ fatigue damage evolution, variable loading.

1 Abstract

The effect of constant and variable amplitude loading on the damage accumulation in $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ angle-ply and $[45]_8$ off-axis carbon-epoxy laminates has been investigated by monitoring the progressive strain changes and examining the related microstructure. The tests were conducted at a frequency of 10 Hz under stress control with stress ratios ($R = \text{min/max stress}$) of 0.1 and -1.0. Variable amplitude fatigue tests at constant stress ratios and at variable stress ratios resulted in lifetimes greater than unity, compared to constant amplitude tests.

2 Introduction

Technical information regarding the cyclic damage performance of polymer matrix composites during stain rate and load fluctuations, as well as unexpected overloads, are important for designing structural applications.

With this as the aim, the purpose of the present work is to apply a parameter that expresses the progressive matrix damage evolution in cyclically loaded carbon fibre epoxy composites. Once established, this parameter can be used to express and predict the total damage during constant and variable amplitude loading conditions.

3 Experimental Procedure

The experimental procedure involved conducting a series of tensile and fatigue tests on HTA (12K) carbon fibre (58% V_f) pre-impregnated 6376 epoxy samples. Table 1 lists the mechanical properties of the fibre, matrix and composites

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of the Fibre, Matrix and Composite.

Mechanical Properties	Carbon Fibre HTA (12K)	Epoxy 6376	Laminate	
			$[45]_8$ Tension	$[\pm 45]_{2S}$ Tension
E-Modulus [GPa]	238	3.6	15.89 ± 0.25	21.24 ± 0.46
Strength [MPa] σ_{uts}	3400	105	109.88 ± 14.65	188.37 ± 2.40
Ultimate Strain [%]	1.4	3.1	0.90 ± 0.20	5.17 ± 2.46
Density [gcm ⁻³]	1.78	1.31	1.58	1.58

Flat test specimens, 180mm long, 16mm wide, 1mm thick were prepared from pre-impregnated plates stacked in a $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ angle-ply or $[45]_8$ off-axis configuration. For the angle-ply laminate the stacking order of the plies was $[+45, -45, +45, -45]_s$, with special care taken to ensure the correct fibre angle of all layers.

Glass fibre/epoxy tabs 1mm thick were adhesively attached at the ends of the specimens to prevent any damage caused by the grips, reducing the free length to 100mm.

All the mechanical testing was performed at room temperature on an Instron servo-hydraulic universal testing machine.

The tensile and compression tests were carried out with a constant actuator speed of 2mm/min. Stress-strain data was acquired from the load cell and strain gauges attached to the specimens.

Compression tests were conducted using an anti-buckling guide consisting of two aluminum plates

bolted together on each side of the specimen with a reduced width of 10mm. Teflon slides were attached to the plates next to the specimens in order to reduce friction. The tests were conducted with strain gauges adhesively attached. Static compression testing gave similar results to those recorded during tensile testing.

Constant amplitude fatigue tests were conducted at a frequency of 10 Hz with a sinusoidal waveform. Stress ratios ($R = \text{minimum}/\text{maximum stress}$) of 0.1, and -1.0 were applied. The strains were measured using gauges and calibrated ram displacements. This allowed damage evolution to be monitored using the fatigue modulus, E_f , defined as the slope of the line connecting the origin of a stress-strain hysteresis loop to the maximum stress for a given cycle, N , as shown in Fig. 1 below.

Fig.1. Cyclic stress- strain hysteresis loops

Crack development was monitored by applying acetate replicas to the test specimen surface after a given number of cycles. The replicas were examined in a scanning electron microscope. In addition, the crack densities and lengths were measured.

4. Results

4.1 Tensile Tests

The tensile stress-strain diagrams for the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ angle-ply and $[45]_8$ off-axis composites are shown in Figure 2.

Although there were the same number of plies in the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ and $[45]_8$ laminates, the former displayed a higher elastic modulus and failure strain due to the stacking sequence. The angle-ply specimens sustained and recorded a larger strain, demonstrating

Fig.2. Stress-strain curves for $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ angle-ply and $[45]_8$ off-axis composites

the ability to undergo more displacement and damage, while maintaining a constant stress level. The interply layers allowed more matrix and fibre damage to accumulate due to load transfer and fibre alignment before final fracture occurred. This was particularly apparent in the greater strain to failure and higher ultimate strength, given in Table 1 above. Although matrix cracks initially formed in both lay-ups the lack of damage tolerance due to fewer crack impediments in the $[45]_8$ off-axis composite allowed major cracks to develop and propagate quickly. In contrast, the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ composite was able to absorb and sustain more damage in the individual plies due to inhomogeneous stress distribution in the matrix resulting in numerous non-propagating microcracks. With increasing stress the matrix deformed, orienting the fibres towards the loading direction, particularly in the angle-ply composite allowing more damage to accumulate.

Petermann [1] observed the same behavior on cyclic testing the angle-ply composite.

4.2 Fatigue Tests

4.2.1 Constant Amplitude

Off-Axis $[45]_8$ Laminate

Constant amplitude fatigue tests with a stress ratio $R = 0.1$ were initially conducted on the $[45]_8$ off-axis laminate. The stress-cycles to failure data is given in Fig.3 below.

Fig.3. Constant amplitude fatigue [45]₈ off-axis composite. R = 0.1

The relationship between the maximum applied stress σ_{max} and the number of cycles to failure N_f is expressed by,

$$\sigma_{max} = 97.05 - 7.55 \log N_f \text{ MPa} \quad (1)$$

This relation is in very good agreement with that recorded earlier by Sorensen [2] for the same composite. Normalizing Eq.1 with respect to the tensile strength of the composite gives,

$$\sigma_{max}/\sigma_{uts} = 0.95 - 0.073 \log N_f \quad (2)$$

Constant amplitude fatigue tests with stress ratio R = -1 were also carried out on a [45]₂₀ off-axis laminate in addition to the [45]₈ off-axis laminate. The resulting stress-cycles to failure data are given by the relation,

$$\sigma_{max} = 123.3 - 11.9 \log N_f \text{ MPa} \quad (3)$$

On normalizing this relationship with respect to tensile strength,

$$\sigma_{max}/\sigma_{uts} = 0.80 - 0.078 \log N_f \quad (4)$$

Angle-Ply [± 45]_{2S} Laminate

Constant amplitude fatigue tests were carried out on the angle-ply [± 45]_{2S} laminate with stress ratios of

Fig.4. Constant amplitude S-N results [± 45]_{2S}. R = 0.1 and R = -1.0

R = 0.1 and R = -1.0. The stress-cycles to failure data are shown in Fig.4 above. For these constant amplitude tests the relation between the maximum applied stress σ_{max} and the number of cycles to failure N_f is expressed by,

$$R = 0.1, \sigma_{max} = 209.66 - 17.50 \log N_f \text{ MPa} \quad (4)$$

$$R = -1.0, \sigma_{max} = 164.20 - 19.02 \log N_f \text{ MPa} \quad (5)$$

In comparison to the off-axis test specimen results, the angle-ply specimens recorded significantly larger strains for a given stress, σ_f , demonstrating the ability of the angle-ply composite to absorb more energy and sustain more damage while maintaining the constant stress level.

Normalizing Equations (4) and (5) with respect to the ultimate tensile strength of the angle-ply [± 45]_{2S} laminate gives,

$$R = 0.1, \sigma_{max}/\sigma_{uts} = 1.26 - 0.106 \log N_f \quad (6)$$

$$R = -1, \sigma_{max}/\sigma_{uts} = 0.87 - 0.099 \log N_f \quad (7)$$

Fatigue Damage Development

Throughout the fatigue life of each composite, damage developed in two main stages. The number, length, and distribution of the cracks were monitored and measured.

Fig.5. Development of shear cracks throughout the fatigue life for R= 0.1.

Fig.5 above shows the number and length of shear cracks that formed and propagated throughout Stages I and II when cycling at stress ratio R= 0.1, representing evolution of the total fatigue damage taking place in these two main stages. Stage I and Stage II damage development are represented in Figs. 6 and 7.

Fig. 6. Two stage fatigue damage development.

In Stage I, on initial cycling a rapid increase in the damage occurred in the form of matrix shear cracking, as shown in Fig 5.

The relationship between crack density and fatigue modulus (stiffness) in Stage I has been considered by several authors [3-5] using different approaches. Plumtree and Shen [6] described the initial matrix damage taking place in Stage I using an exponential fitting function in the form of the classic two parameter Weibull model and expressed the longitudinal component of the damage tensor D^I for a given number of cycles, N by,

$$D^I = D_1 \{1 - \exp[-N/\alpha]^\beta\} \quad (8)$$

where D_1 is the balance between the amount of damage and the applied stress at the characteristic damage state corresponding to the exhaustion of microcracking at the end of the first stage.

For the angle-ply composite, the scale factor α , was found to be sensitive to cyclic stress, whereas β was approximately constant, with a value of unity.

Hence Stage I damage can be expressed by,

$$R = 0.1, D^I = 0.0033\sigma - 0.259, \alpha = 10814 - 69.29\sigma \quad (9)$$

$$R = -1.0, D^I = 0.0014\sigma + 0.048, \alpha = 21937 - 199.33\sigma \quad (10)$$

Fig.7. Fatigue damage development in $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ angle-ply composite for 65 and 110MPa. R= -1.0.

In the both the first and second stages, the amount of damage increased with cyclic stress as seen in Fig. 7 above which follows the damage development throughout the life of the angle-ply $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ composite at two stress levels of 65 and 110 MPa for $R = -1.0$. Fatigue modulus plots for $R = 0.1$ cyclic tests conducted at maximum stresses of 115 and 155 MPa showed the same trends.

Stage I is complete when matrix cracking reaches saturation as shown in Fig. 5. This leads into Stage II, in which the damage accumulates at a slower rate. Crack coalescence and delamination occur and continue to develop over the remainder of the life (90%). During this second stage, fibre debonding and final fibre fracture develop. Equilibrium is established between the applied load and crack density.

Since damage evolution throughout this second stage involves the propagation of microcracks, it is possible that the growth rate could be expressed by the Paris equation. However, for multi-damage mechanisms there is no clear definition of crack length for these microcracks and the crack tip stress intensity factor.

This was taken into account by Plumtree and Shen [6] by replacing the crack length with a damage mechanics counterpart, thereby providing a descriptive parameter for the fatigue damage, expressed by:

$$D^{II} = D_2 \{1 - (1 - [N/N_f]^\gamma)\} \quad (11)$$

D_2 is the critical amount of damage, D^{II} at end of the second stage. For the $[\pm 45]$ angle-ply carbon-epoxy composite, the second stage damage evolution was linear and the exponent γ constant, equal to unity [7]. In this case, fatigue damage evolution for Stage II is then simply expressed by:

$$D^{II} = D_2 (N/N_f) \quad (12)$$

$$D_2 = 0.0033\sigma - 0.289 \quad \text{for } R = 0.1 \quad (13)$$

$$D_2 = 0.0028\sigma - 0.066 \quad \text{for } R = -1.0 \quad (14)$$

The total damage D_T accumulated in the composite after N_F cycles is the combination of damage in Stages I and II, given by,

$$D_T = D_1 \{1 - \exp[-N/\alpha]^\beta\} + D_2 \{1 - (1 - [N/N_f]^\gamma)\} \quad (15)$$

4.2.2 Variable Amplitude Fatigue Tests

Two types of variable amplitude fatigue tests were conducted. The application was similar and the following is a general description.

One group of specimens (H-L) was cycled at a high stress level (H) and then at a low stress (L) level. The second group (L-H) was cycled at the low stress level and then cycled at the high stress level. These tests were either conducted at the same or different stress ratios.

In both cases the initial stress level was applied for a given number of cycles (N_1) based on the percentage of known fatigue life (N_1/N_{f1}) at the particular stress level according to the constant amplitude tests on which these tests were based. Upon completion of N_1 cycles, the stress level was changed and the test continued at the new stress level for a pre-determined number of cycles (N_2) until failure occurred or the number of cycles exceeded one million, at which point the test was stopped.

The two groups of variable amplitude fatigue tests were:

1. Constant stress ratio tests

a) $R = 0.1$ tests were conducted on the off-axis $[45]_8$ composite, and

b) $R = -1$ tests on the angle-ply $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ composite.

2. Variable stress ratio tests

Tests at $R = 0.1$ (H) and $R = -1$ (L) tests were conducted at a constant maximum stress corresponding to a fatigue life of 50,000 cycles.

1. Constant Stress Ratio Tests

a) Off-axis $[45]_8$ Laminate

Fatigue tests with a constant stress ratio of ratio of $R = 0.1$ were carried out on the unidirectional off-axis $[45]_8$ composite in order to determine the effect of variable two stage (high and low) loading on the basic properties of the material.

The two stress levels tested were 55MPa for the low (L) and 75MPa for the high stress (H). The choice of these stress levels was determined because of the significant difference in the fatigue life of these two levels was more than one decade and failure occurred after a relatively high number of cycles. The estimated fatigue life was 3400 cycles for the high stress and 370000 cycles for the low level stress. Fourteen H-L and L-H tests were conducted.

Fig.8. Variable amplitude R= 0.1. Off-axis [45]₈.

The change from the high to low stress level, or vice versa, was conducted on reaching a predetermined fraction of the fatigue life at the corresponding stress level.

Fig.8 above shows the variable amplitude fatigue results based on the lives given by Eqn. 1. All the variable amplitude fatigue test samples tested at the high-low (H-L) or low-high (L-H) levels had total lives greater than those of single amplitude tests at the corresponding stress. Hence, as Fig. 8 shows, the damage summation of the two fatigue life fractions for each test exceeded unity.

With regard to specimens HL 03.20 and HL 03 21 shown in Fig. 8 with arrows attached, the first (HL 03.20) failed after 255022 cycles at the high stress following 6.89 million cycles at the low stress, resulting in a Miner life summation of 214. Sample HL 03.21 failed after 14.46 million cycles at the low stress following 1720 cycles at the high stress resulting in a Miner life summation of 51.

b) Angle-Ply [± 45]_{2S} Laminate

Constant stress ratio R= -1 Angle-Ply [± 45]_{2S}

The maximum stresses of 110MPa for the high stress (H) and 65MPa for the low stress (L) were chosen because the difference in the mean fatigue lives at each stress level was greater than one decade, with little overlap occurring in their fatigue lives. The variable amplitude fatigue results are given in Figure 9.

Fig.9. Variable amplitude fatigue [± 45]_{2S} R= -1

In all cases, the accumulated life fraction exceeded unity. The test sequence had no significant effect, regardless of whether the low or high maximum stresses occurred first. For the initial high stress, a large number of well distributed matrix cracks formed. On changing to the lower stress more cracks were present than required to maintain the reduced stress level. Consequently, the local stress intensity decreased with an accompanying decrease in the crack opening displacement. Also, additional closure resulted from matrix debris becoming trapped in the cracks. The effective intensity factor range was then reduced delaying failure, resulting in an increased life. Considering the low to high stress tests, additional cycles were required to increase the matrix crack density in order to balance the internal stress created by the higher applied load, delaying the transition to the second stage.

2. Variable Stress Ratio

Angle-Ply [± 45]_{2S} Laminate

For this series of tests R=0.1 represented the high stress (H) and R= -1 the low stress (L) based on their maximum applied stresses. The results are shown in Figure 10.

In all cases the specimens exceeded a combined life ratio of unity. Changing from R= 0.1 high stress (128MPa) to the R= -1 low stress (75MPa), the maximum applied stress decreased and crack closure occurred during the compression part of the cycle. For the R= 0.1 to R= -1 series of tests, numerous well distributed matrix cracks formed during the first R= 0.1 (high stress) stage. On changing to the lower

Fig. 10. Variable stress ratio $R= 0.1$ and $R= -1$. $[\pm 45]_{2S}$

stress level ($R= -1$), stress relaxation occurred resulting in reduced crack opening displacement, in a similar manner to the variable amplitude tests at constant $R= -1$, for high to low stress level changes. Consequently more cycles were required at the lower stress level for the cracks to continue propagating. The lower stress intensity and debris accumulation in the cracks accounted for the increased life.

For the second series of tests, the stress ratio was changed from $R= -1$ to $R= 0$, hence changing from low to high stress levels. This required a larger number of cycles to increase the matrix crack density in order to balance the internal stress created by the previous higher applied load, thereby delaying the transition from the first to second stage damage, resulting in longer lives.

5 Discussion

The cyclic results of the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ angle-ply carbon-epoxy composite clearly demonstrated that this structure is more tolerant to fatigue damage and failure than the off-axis $[45]_{2S}$ composite. This is particularly evident, considering its higher fatigue limit stress when cycled at the same stress ratio. The $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ angle-ply composite absorbed considerably more energy than the $[45]_8$ composite before failure. Higher interlaminar shear stresses develop in the angle-ply composite on stressing the composite, allowing individual laminae to rotate closer to the loading direction while maintaining specimen

alignment. Herakovich et al. [8] observed fibre rotation of up to 10° in a carbon fibre-polyimide composite before failure occurred. It is interesting to note that the failure was caused by instability rather than fibre failure [9]. Also, Trappe et al. [10] showed that on statically straining $[\pm 45]$ GFRP laminates, the fibres realigned 9.2% closer to the loading direction.

The response to tensile loading of a $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate is dominated by shear, whereas shear is minimal in the $[45]_8$ laminate. The high shear strength of the cross-ply laminate results in its greater ability to withstand and absorb more micro and macroscopic damage. Consequently the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate displays a large inelastic strain prior to final fracture.

Cyclic stress-strain hysteresis loops for both laminates were recorded during testing and analyzed. A comparison of the representative hysteresis loop opening strains for tests performed at stresses between 51% and 67% tensile strength is given in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Comparison of cyclic angle-ply and off-axis hysteresis loop openings.

The hysteresis loops for the angle-ply composite are significantly wider (about 40%) compared to those of the off-axis specimens indicating that more potential energy is absorbed during cycling.

Considering the laminate lay-up, the angle-ply samples present a more difficult path for fracture than the angle-ply, requiring more energy for crack propagation. Since each 45ply is stacked alternately, deformation in opposite directions and shear displacement or interlaminar failure is resisted under stress in order to maintain the original loading

direction [11]. In addition, the shear occurring within each lamina tends to rotate the fibres [9]. Hence the fracture path becomes more complex than that for the off-axis lay-up resulting in more energy being required for failure, as seen in the larger hysteresis loop opening strain, shown in Fig. 11.

Conclusions

1. The angle-ply lay-up of the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ composite allowed the material to sustain more fatigue damage than the unidirectional off-axis $[45]_8$ composite.
2. Variable amplitude fatigue tests on both the unidirectional off-axis $[45]_8$ and angle-ply $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates resulted in lifetimes greater than unity when compared to constant amplitude stress tests conducted on the composites.
3. On changing from lower to higher stress levels, the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ composite required additional cycles to increase the matrix crack density in order to balance the internal stress created by the higher applied load, delaying the transition from the first to second stage damage. This resulted in longer fatigue lives. For high to low stress level changes, the accompanying stress relaxation in the fatigue specimens containing large numbers of matrix cracks resulted in reduced crack opening displacement. A lower stress intensity and debris accumulation in the cracks accounted for the increased life.
4. Similarly, variable amplitude fatigue tests on the unidirectional off-axis $[45]_8$ composite resulted in total lives longer than those of the single amplitude tests at the corresponding stress.

References

- [1] J. Petermann and K. Schulte "Strain based service time estimation for angle-ply laminates". *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol. 62, pp 1043-1050, 2002.
- [2] L. Sorensen "Cyclic damage evolution in a 45° off-axis carbon fibre reinforced epoxy reinforced composite". MAsc Thesis, University of Waterloo, 2002.
- [3] S.F.L. Matthews and R.D. Rawlings "Composite materials: engineering and science". Woodhead Publishing Limited, 1999.
- [4] Z. Gao "A Cumulative damage model for fatigue life of composite materials". *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 13, pp128-141, 1994.

- [5] W.B. Hwang and K.S. Han "Fatigue of composite materials: damage model and life prediction in composite materials." *Fatigue and Fracture, Second volume, ASTM STP 1012*, Paul A. Legace Ed. ASTM, Philadelphia, pp.87-10, 1989.
- [6] A. Plumtree and G. Shen "Prediction of fatigue damage development in unidirectional long fibre composites", *Polymers and Polymer Composites*, Vol. 2, pp. 83-90, 1994.
- [7] J. Lemaitre and A. Plumtree "Application of damage concepts to predict creep-fatigue failure". *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, Vol.101, pp. 284-292, 1979.
- [8] C.T. Herakovich, R.D. Schroedter III, A. Gasser and L. Giutard "Damage evolution in $[\pm 45]$ laminates with fibre rotation", *Composite Science and Technology*, Vol.60, pp. 2771-2789, 2000.
- [9] C.T. Herakovich "Mechanics of fibrous composites". J. Wiley and Sons, 1998.
- [10] V. Trappe, M. P. Hentschel and H. Ivers "Determination of inter-fibre failure in complex, reinforced composites". *Proceedings of 16th European Conference of Fracture*, paper no. 900, Springer 2006, ISBN 1-4020-4971-4, pp.1-8.
- [11] D. Hull "An introduction to composite materials", Cambridge University Press, 1981.

Acknowledgments

The author wishes to thank the Natural Sciences and Engineering Council of Canada for financial assistance.

The technical assistance of Mark Melo, University of Waterloo, is gratefully acknowledged. Thanks are due to Professor Dr-Ing. Karl Schulte, Technical University of Hamburg-Harburg, Germany, and Dr-Ing. Jorge Petermann, Air Bus Ltd., Hamburg, Germany for providing the material and stimulating discussions.